

A new species of *Salicarus* (Hemiptera: Miridae: Phylinae) from Morocco

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Abstract: *Salicarus maroccanus* sp. nov. is described from Morocco, representing the first record of the genus *Salicarus* in North Africa. A differential diagnosis is provided, together with illustrations of the male and female genitalia and photographs of the dorsal habitus of the new species. A modified key couplet is also provided to incorporate the new species into the key to *Salicarus* species by Konstantinov & Hosseini (2024).

Keywords: North Africa, taxonomy, plant bugs

Introduction

This paper provides a description of a new species of plant bug (Miridae), the most species-rich family of true bugs (Heteroptera), many of which are host-specific. The family is particularly diverse in Mediterranean ecosystems (Cassis & Schuh, 2012) and remains insufficiently studied even within the Palaearctic region, both in terms of generic and higher-level classification and in the discovery of new species.

The genus *Salicarus* Kerzhner, 1962 has a complex taxonomic history and was redefined by Konstantinov (2023) to include nine species. More recently, Konstantinov & Hosseini (2024) provided a comprehensive revision of the genus, including an illustrated key to species, redescriptions, and recognition of three species groups: the *S. nitidus* group, the *S. roseri* group, and the *S. fulvicornis* group. The first group comprises four small (2.0–2.8 mm) stumpy species densely clothed with broad silvery scales, and with distinctly swollen antennal segments I and II.

These species are distributed in Mediterranean Europe, from Spain to Cyprus, and feed on legumes of the tribe Genisteeae. The *S. roseri* species group includes three species with variable colouration, large oval body (3.0–4.0 mm) and narrow scalelike setae which are sparsely distributed only on the hemelytra and/or thoracic pleura. All three feed exclusively on *Salix* spp. and occur in Central and Western Asia, with *S. roseri*, the type species of the genus, having a broader Euro-Siberian distribution (Konstantinov & Zinovyeva, 2017). The *S. fulvicornis* species group comprises two species distributed mainly in Central Asia and Mongolia, and feeding on *Caragana* spp. They are variable in colouration, with the dorsum densely covered with narrow scales. Males are elongate and parallel-sided (3.6–4.0 mm), while females are shorter and ovoid (3.5–3.9 mm).

Recent collecting in Morocco revealed a new species belonging to the *S. fulvicornis* species group based on vesica structure and body shape. However, it clearly differs from all *Salicarus* spp. in several characters, including a vestiture composed solely of

simple setae, without scales on dorsum or thoracic pleurites. In addition, the discovery of this species substantially expands the known distribution of the genus, which was previously undocumented in North Africa.

Materials and methods

Photographs of the habitus were taken using a Keyence VHX-5000 digital microscope. Genitalic structures were examined and photographed using Zeiss Axioscope 5 equipped with a Canon EOS 700D digital camera. Partially focused images of each specimen or structure were stacked using Helicon Focus software. All measurements were taken using a calibrated eyepiece graticule and are given in millimetres. Terminology for the male genitalia follows Konstantinov (2019), with additional details illustrated in Fig. 13 of Konstantinov (2008), while terminology for the female genitalia follows Davis (1955) and Schwartz (2011). The holotype and one paratype of the new species are deposited in the Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris (MNHN), six paratypes are in the personal collection of A. Matocq, and two paratypes are housed in the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia (NMNHS).

Taxonomic account

Salicarus maroccanus sp. n. (Figs 1–3)

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Type material. Holotype: ♂, Morocco: Souss-Massa region, Environs of Aqesri, N 30° 37', W 9° 30', 207 m a.s.l., 06 May 2009, A. Matocq leg., MNHN (EH 31947).

Paratypes: 1 ♀, same locality label as holotype, MNHN (EH 31948). 6 ♀♀, same locality label as holotype. Matocq coll. (Paris). 1 ♂, same locality label as holotype, NMNHS. Morocco: Marrakesh-Safi region: 1 ♀, Route S501, Ijoukak, Caidat de Talat-n-Yakoub, N 30° 59', W 08° 10', 02 May 2000, A. Matocq leg., NMNHS.

Diagnosis. Recognised by the following combination of characters: Body in male elongate,

almost parallel sized, total length 3.6–4.0 (Fig. 1A), female more stumpy, 2.8–3.2 (Fig. 1B); dorsum and appendages uniformly dark brown to black; segment II thin, rod-shaped; vestiture composed of adpressed dense simple setae only, without scales on dorsum or thoracic pleura; vesica strongly coiled at middle, with long, thin, and almost straight apical blades closely adjoined along their entire length (Fig. 2A, B).

Salicarus maroccanus sp. n. is a distinctive species that can be easily distinguished from its congeners. It is most similar in body colouration, size, and body proportions of both sexes to the predominantly Mongolian *S. fulvicornis*. However, the latter is easily separated by the presence of dense flattened scales on the dorsum and a comparatively smaller secondary gonopore. *Salicarus roseri*, the only species of the genus lacking scales on the dorsum, differs from the new species in several characters including the presence of scale-like setae on the thoracic pleura, a yellow pattern even in the darkest-coloured specimens (e.g., yellow tibiae, apices of femora, and the last two antennal segments), and an ovoid body shape in males. All species of *S. fulvicornis* and *S. roseri* species groups further differ from the new species by having diverging apical blades of the vesica (fig. 7 in Konstantinov & Hosseini, 2024). In contrast, the vesica of *S. maroccanus*, equipped with long, thin, apical blades closely adpressed along their entire length, is somewhat similar to that of the *S. nitidus* group (fig. 8 in Konstantinov & Hosseini, 2024), but differs in the straight shape of the apical blades and the smaller secondary gonopore. Furthermore, species of the *S. nitidus* group greatly differ from the new species in all other respects, including smaller overall size, stouter body, incrassate antennal segments I and II, and a dorsum densely clothed with broad scales.

Description. Male. Colouration. Uniformly dark brown to black (Fig. 1). Head: Dark brown to black; antenna dark brown, with slightly paler segments III and IV, labium dark brown with black segment IV. Thorax: Pronotum, scutellum, and thoracic pleurites uniformly dark brown to black, hemelytron uniformly brown to dark brown, with semitransparent pale brown membrane; coxae, femora, tibiae, and tarsi dark brown, without additional markings. Abdomen: Uniformly dark brown to black.

Surface and vestiture. Dorsum shining, smooth, with weakly rugose hemelytron; pronotum, scutellum, and hemelytron clothed with dense brown

Fig. 1. Habitus of *S. maroccanus* sp. nov.: A – male dorsal view; B – female dorsal view; C – male head and thorax in lateral view.

simple setae, semierect and longer at sides of pronotum and hemelytron, shorter and adpressed elsewhere; antenna, legs, and venter covered with similar but shorter and sometimes dirty whitish setae, scarce on thoracic pleurites, dense elsewhere; tibial spines black.

Structure. Body elongate, almost parallel-sided, 3.1–3.4× as long as posterior width of pronotum; total length 3.6–4.0; Head: Vertical, slightly protruding beyond eyes anteriorly and ventrally; vertex flat,

posteriorly distinctly attenuate (Fig. 1C), 1.6–2.0× as wide as eye; frons weakly convex; clypeus flat, barely visible in dorsal view; antenna inserted near ventral margin of eye; antennal segment short, cylindrical; segment II rod-shaped, slightly thinner than segment I, 0.7× as long as posterior width of pronotum, subequal to width of head; segments III and IV filiform; labium reaching mesocoxa. Thorax: Pronotum trapezoidal, with indistinct calli and broadly rounded anterior and posterior corners, 2.4×

Fig. 2. Male genitalia of *S. maroccanus* sp. nov.: A – vesica in left lateral view; B – apex of vesica, magnified, in right lateral view; C – right paramere; D – left paramere; E – apex of phallosome.

as wide as long, 1.4–1.6× as wide as head; metathoracic scent gland evaporatory area broadly triangular, peritreme oval, apically rounded. Legs:

Comparatively short, femora swollen, broader medially, tibia cylindrical, tarsal segment short, segment II 1.3 × as long as segment I, segment III 1.5

Fig. 3. Female genitalia and male claw of *S. maroccanus* sp. nov.: A – dorsal labiate plate of the bursa copulatrix; B – bursa copulatrix on ventral view, showing sclerites encircling vulva and vestibulum; C – posterior wall of bursa copulatrix; D – male hind claw.

× as long as I and 1.2 × as long as II; claw (Fig. 3D) gradually bent from midpoint, pulvillus distinctly surpassing midpoint of claw, attached along its entire length; parempodium setiform, not apically spatulate.

Genitalia. Right paramere small, broadly oval, with apically blunt apical process (Fig. 2C). Left paramere with straight, comparatively short apical process and thin, roughly triangular, and apically rounded sensory lobe (Fig. 2D). Vesica strongly coiled at middle, with two long and thin, gradually

tapering apical blades closely adjoined along their entire length; larger blade twice as long as smaller one; secondary gonopore comparatively small, located on membrane far from apex, with small gonopore sclerite (Fig. 2A, B).

Female. Colouration, surface and vestiture as in male (Fig. 1B). Structure. Similar to male but body shorter and oval, 2.6–2.9× as long as posterior width of pronotum, total length 2.8–3.2; head with slightly more convex frons and clypeus, and with smaller

eyes, vertex 2.0–2.2 × as wide as eye; antennal segment II somewhat thinner than in male and distinctly thinner than segment I, 0.6–0.7× as long as posterior width of pronotum, 0.8–0.9× as long as width of head; pronotum 2.3–2.5× as wide as long, 1.3–1.4× as wide as head.

Genitalia. Dorsal labiate plate with large and broadly oval sclerotised rings (Fig. 3A). Sclerites encircling vulva triangular, symmetrical (Fig. 3B). Vestibulum characteristically long, S-shaped (Fig. 3B). Posterior wall clothed with dense fine spinules and longitudinal sclerotised bands at sides (Fig. 3C).

Distribution. Known from two localities in Souss-Massa and Marrakesh-Safi regions of Morocco.

Host. Unknown.

Discussion. *Salicarus maroccanus* sp. n. is assigned to the respective genus based on the diagnosis outlined in Konstantinov (2023) and a combination of characters including the strongly flattened and sloping head with the clypeus barely visible from above, the posteriorly carinate vertex, the contrastingly large, S-shaped vestibulum of the bursa copulatrix, the broadly rounded right paramere, the vesica strongly coiled at middle, with two gradually tapering apical blades that remain fused along most of their length, and the secondary gonopore with a small gonopore sclerite. However, two characters set this species, otherwise belonging to the *S. fulvicornis* species group, from congeners: the absence of scale-like setae and the setiform, rather than apically spatulate parempodium. The latter feature was documented in detail by Schwartz & Stonedahl (2004) and has previously been considered one of the non-unique synapomorphies uniting the *Salicarus* + *Phoenicocoris* clade (Konstantinov, 2023). Spatulate parempodia have also been reported in otherwise unrelated taxa, such as *Campylomma* spp. (Konstantinov et al., 2015), and *Mesopsallus* spp. (Schwartz & Stonedahl, 2004; Konstantinov, 2023). Broader comparative studies of pretarsal structures are therefore required to clarify the distribution and evolutionary significance of this character.

Phoenicocoris vidali (Lindberg, 1940), a poorly known species, was originally described from nine males and a single female collected in Ras-el-Ma, Atlas Moutains, Morocco, and placed in the genus *Sthenarus*. The species is still apparently known only from the type series, some specimens of which were later studied by Wagner, who provided a redescription and schematic drawings of the male genitalia,

including the vesica (fig. 2k in Wagner, 1960, reprinted as fig. 699b1 in Wagner 1975). According to Wagner (1960: 11), the vesica is S-shaped, twisted, slender, of simple structure, distally with two unequal, slender chitinous rods, alongside a membranous area. Wagner (1975: 105) further described it as very slender, with the apical part strongly curved and bearing two closely adjoining long chitinous rods. In their comprehensive revision of *Phoenicocoris*, Schwartz & Stonedahl (2004) supported the placement of *P. vidali* within the genus based on these descriptions. However, direct examination of the vesica of this species is still highly desirable for unequivocal generic assignment, given the close relationship between *Phoenicocoris* and *Salicarus* and their reliable separation based on male genitalia. In any case, *P. vidali* is clearly distinct from *S. maroccanus* sp. n. in several characters, including its smaller body size (2.2–2.4 mm), short antennal segment II (subequal to head width and distinctly swollen, spindle-shaped in males and somewhat club-shaped, distally dilated in females), and yellow fore and middle legs with darkened apices of femora.

The new species may be incorporated into the key presented by Konstantinov & Hosseini (2024) by modifying couplet 5 and adding a new couplet 6 as follows:

5. Hemelytron without scale-like setae, clothed only with simple setae 6
- Hemelytron clothed with a mixture of simple setae and narrow, apically acuminate scale-like setae (sometimes scarce and easily obliterated) (fig. 3C, F, I in Konstantinov & Hosseini 2024) 7 (6 in Konstantinov & Hosseini 2024)
6. Body of male ovoid; colouration variable in both sexes, but even the darkest specimens with dirty yellow tibiae and apices of femora; dorsum often with additional yellow markings (fig. 2F–I in Konstantinov & Hosseini 2024). Thoracic pleura clothed with scale-like setae. Vesica with straight, robust, diverging apical blades (fig. 7G, H in Konstantinov & Hosseini 2024). Widely distributed in the Palearctic. On *Salix* spp. *S. roseri*
- Body of male parallel-sided; both sexes uniformly dark brown to brown. Thoracic pleura without scale-like setae. Vesica with thin, straight apical blades closely adjoining along their entire length (fig. 2A, B). Morocco *S. maroccanus* sp. n.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the authors, reviewers, or subject editor. As a member of the editorial board Fedor Konstantinov recused himself from discussions and decisions on the manuscript.

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